

Table 4

Grid 2. Observation/habitat on new 30 STEM edutubers by channel, description and gender (with YouTube Spain). Total: 33 channels

Mathematics	Description	Gender
42. DotCSV, Santi García Cremades	Artificial intelligence: In-depth análisis of the most interesting topics, <i>Machine Learning</i> , algorithms and opinión articles	Man
43. Raiz de PI	Mathematics: current affairs integrating statistics, with humor and channels that he loves (biology)	Man
11. Derivando	Mathematics: number, Gauss, Pitágoras theorem, Euler and videos that he loves (physics, biology)	Man
Natural Sciences		
44. Vary Ingweion	Curious biology with humorous character	Man
45. La Hiperactina	Curiosities of the human body, organism, microbiology, metabolism, genetics, to study biomedicine and featured channels	Woman
46. Dietética Sin Patrocinadores	<i>Hangouts</i> , conferences and health (radio program). Dietetic, food industry, long videos, recording in open spaces (videoconferences with several, round tables, presentations in events). Usually long videos (more than one hour)	Mixed
47. Preventiva et al	Medicine with humor. Gests and favorite music selection	Man
48. Ciencia XL	Quantum physics, CERN matters, Cosmos, Physics experiemnts and featured channels. Note: brief female appearance	Man
49. El Alimentólogo, José Kenji	Scientific teaching. Food with humorous character, important figures in the fitness sector, anecdotes with nutritionists, debates y anecdotes with male and female guests	Man
50. Cerebrotos	Neurotransmitters, book reviews, articles, advices for thesis	Woman
51. Alimentación Holística	Experiments, cosmetics recipes, to cooking, curiosities	Woman
52. Mi dieta cojea	Nutrition questions, TEDx talks, conferences, eating better	Man
53. Deborahciencia, Débora García Bello	Science, food, art, criticism, interviews, book reviews	Woman
54. Huele a Química	Cosmetic chemistry	Man
55. Antroporama	Scientific teaching, Chemistry	Woman
56. Patri Tezanos	Scientific tecahing about the human being, ciencia del amor y la atracción, fenómenos, consciencia, test y experimentos	Woman
57. Geological Legacy	Geology and geological Minecraft	Man
58. Ciencias de la Ciencia	Cosmos, stars, biographies, scientific curiosities, theory of everything, and other channels	Man
59. La gata de Schrödinger, R. Vidal	Reports, critical issues, debates, sexuality	Woman
60. Sinapsis	Creativity and brind, music, painting, dance, literature and brind	Woman
61. CdeCiencia	Physics: Cosmos, videotutorials and megatutorials, news	Man
28. Date un Vlog	A new way of understanding education. Speculative physics, cosmology, astronomy, quantum physics and relativity	Man
21. Quantum Fracture	Scientific teaching of physics and dissemination of time, gravity, electricity	Man
62. FISICALIMITE	Physics	Man
63. Diario de un MIR, Paul Mateo	Medicine: news, Avant-garde, history of medicine, personal development and life as a doctor	Man
64. Glóbulo Azul	Medicine, drugs, body-mind	Man
65. Viajando por Planetas, Laura M. Parro	Pre-doctoral student in Planetary Science	Woman
66. SizeMatters	Robots, nanoscience, atoms, materials	Woman
67. Sábados culturetas	Experiments, nature with hints of humor	Woman
68. CienciadeSofa, Jordi Pereira	Physics: periodical table, meteorites, chemistry	Man
69. Sígueme la corriente	Renewable energy: electricity, concepts y news	Man
70. WillDiv	Biology y scientific teaching, heroes y villains, Disney biology, parasites. Lot of cartoons with links to popular cartoons roles. Guidance (if you go to the university...)	Man
71. CERNtripetas, Héctor García	Physics (closed)	Man